

higher than 3 times that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain the virus.

Both rice accessions and six weed species were infected with RSV (see table). Infected *Oryza* plants showed typical RSV symptoms. Infected *Leersia hexandra* plants also showed symptoms. Weed species not infected with the virus were *Brachiaria distachya*, *B. mutica*, *Chloris barbata*, *Cyperus brevifolius*, *C. difformis*, *Eleusine indica*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with RSV after inoculation by RSV-viruliferous BPH. IRR1.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants (mean)
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>				
Acc. 100882	14	2	0.13-0.48	0.00
Acc. 101397	12	6	0.07-0.29	0.00
<i>O. latifolia</i>	10	3	0.13-4.22	0.01
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	12	1	0.15	0.04
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	12	1	0.17	0.03
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	16	1	0.25	0.00
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i>	12	3	0.12-0.37	0.04
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	12	3	0.10-0.28	0.00
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	28	5	0.06-0.12	0.00

Differential transmission of tungro (RTV) by green leafhopper (GLH) selected on IR54

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We compared RTV transmission by a GLH *Nephotettix virescens* colony maintained since 1982 on resistant variety IR54 in the greenhouse and by a colony on TN1, using a selected set of 12 differential varieties. Seven-day-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated separately at 1 insect/seedling for 24 h, using GLH adults that had fed on RTV-infected Pelita plants. Infection

symptoms (stunting and yellowing) were assessed visually 14 d after inoculation (DAI) and by latex serology 16 DAI.

Higher infection rates were obtained from the IR54 colony on IR28, IR29, IR34, IR50, IR54, IR58, and IR60, with resistances to GLH derived primarily from Gam Pai 30-12-15 (see figure). The latex test showed seedlings mostly were infected with both bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses. Inoculation with the TN1 colony resulted in infection mainly with RTBV alone.

Regardless of colony, IR26 and IR30 had high RTBV infection. IR36 and IR42 had high infection with both viruses.

These results indicate that GLH selected on IR54 have higher ability to transmit RTBV and RTSV on varieties with Gam Pai 30-12-15 in their parentage. Resistance of IR54 to RTV is conditioned only by its resistance to the GLH vector, not to the RTV-associated viruses. □

Infection (%)

RTV incidence based on symptoms and RTBV + RTSV incidence based on the latex test in rice varieties inoculated at 1 insect/seedling in test tubes by TN1 and IR54 GLH colonies that had fed on Cisadane plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV.

Combined ufra + blast (BI) infection in deepwater rice

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Ufra disease caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* is spreading rapidly in the deepwater rice